

SpServ
(Spectrum service and
fitting program)

Manual

Introduction

SpServ is a program for storing and manipulating different 'spectra'. 'Spectrum' in this program means a series (vectors) of (x,y) number pairs. x is usually (but not necessarily) equidistant.

Starting the program will open a completely empty session, with an empty spectrum page. You can create new pages and populate them with spectra by opening them from a file or by calculating.

There are two windows present when you start the SpServ program. The main window of SpServ is something like in Fig. 1. The main part of the window displays the spectra, a command line frame, and different information and set elements on the window. Basically, there are two spectra visible, the so-called 'foreground' and 'background' spectra. Usually, you can manipulate the 'foreground' spectrum. The result of manipulation usually appears in the 'background' spectrum.

While there is only one 'background' spectrum, the number of 'foreground' spectra depends only on the memory available. SpServ can store many spectra, the number of spectra depends only on the memory available. One can imagine the series of 'foreground' spectra as different pages in the program. Every page is numbered sequentially. Changing the 'foreground' spectrum can be achieved by pushing the 'left' and 'right' buttons at the upper right corner of the main window, by hitting the 'up' and 'down' arrows or the 'page up' and 'page down' keys on the keyboard. These will change the serial number by one (increase or decrease by one).

Every 'foreground' spectrum has a serial number and a 'title'. While the title is unique (although it can be changed), the serial number can change since you can delete individual spectra, and in this case, the serial number of consecutive

spectra will change. You can also copy spectra and have two copies of the same spectrum with different serial numbers.

The second window is the “Parameter” window (Fig. 2). It contains the parameters necessary for the fitting.

The content of the window changes during the fit and also depending on the parameters and function to fit. The functions have different fittable parameters (usually 3) and you can fit up to 17 of the same functions (e.g. sum of 17 different Gauss functions).

Parameters in window

File Edit View Insert Tools Desktop Window Help

Parameters for EXPJUMP function(s)

Fitting conditions: Iteration is not limited Cage on Stop if too little steps

Show function Fit

	Amplitude	Position	Width
1. EXPJUMP	245.68	110.86	6.0841
2. EXPJUMP	348.3	133.71	14.634
3. EXPJUMP	3011.83	315.693	13.615
4. EXPJUMP	7770.74	351.005	12.5504

Reading and saving files

The native file format of the SpServ program is the “*.sps” file. It contains all the working place, spectra, etc. you have created in a session. When you load (read) an sps file you will find everything you have put into a session before.

Opening a file can be done using the “File Open” icon in the icon bar, or using the “File->Open” menu command. There

File type selection window

File selection window

are corresponding command line commands as well (see later the commands).

When you open a file a “File selection” window will open. Here you can select what type and which file would you like to open. The default file type is “*.sps”. If you open an “*.sps” file it will replace the session you recently had in the SpServ program (if it is not empty). If you did not save yet the current session the program will ask if you want to save it.

If you open a file other than “*.sps” it will import into the current session starting from the actual serial (page) number. The pages imported will depend on the file type and the number of spectra in the file.

Saving a file can be done by the “Save file” icon on the icon bar or using the menu commands “File->Save” or “File->Save as” or using a specific command. If you click on the “Save File” icon, the session will be saved using the current file name (the file name of the current session can be found at the top of the main SpServ window). If there is no current file name the program opens a “Save spectrum file” window and you can select/define the file name.

The “File->Save as” command always opens the “Save spectrum file” window and you can select the file format you want to use to save (in the case of “*.sps” format) or export the session or the page(s) in the case of other file formats. The explanations of different import and export file formats are discussed in the corresponding commands.

Commands

The universal format of a command is:

commandword parm1 parm2 parmn

where 'commandword' is a command word, parm1 ... parmn are the parameters for the command. The parameters are separated by a space character. The actual number (n) of the parameters depends on the actual command and is explained there.

File input commands

Command: **LOAD** 'filename'

Example: LOAD example.sps

Explanation: This command loads "*.sps" files. If the 'filename' is unique it will load the session from the 'filename'. If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*.sps") the different *.sps files will be concatenated.

Command: **RAXY** filename par1 par2 par3

Example: RAXY examplefile

Explanation: This command reads ASCII files where spectra are in columns. The command reads only one column pair (X,Y) from a single file to the actual page. If both par1 and par2 are missing then it reads the first two columns as X and Y values. If par1 and par2 are present it reads the corresponding columns (par1 column is the X value and par2 column is the Y value). If the par3 parameter is present, the command will omit the first par3 lines of the spectrum (if there is some text, explanation, etc. at the beginning of the file).

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. exam*) all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and the column numbers where the spectrum is read.

Command: RTBL 'filename' omit any

Example: rtbl example

Explanation: This command reads ASCII files where spectra are in columns. The command reads all column pairs (X,Y) from a single file to the actual page.

The parameter 'omit' means that this many lines should be omitted from the beginning of the file. If parameter 'any' is NOT present then the first column is treated as a uniform X value for all the other columns (XYYYYYYYY...Y file structure). If parameter 'any' is present (it might be any character) then the file contains XY columns throughout the file. (XY XY XY XY..... XY file structure).

If both 'omit' and 'any' parameters are missing then XYYYYYYY...Y file structure is assumed.

The different columns (column pairs) in the file will be placed on different, consecutive pages.

If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*") all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last column of the last file is read. The title of the pages will contain the filename and the column numbers where the spectrum is read.

Command: RAY 'filename' omit

Example: RAY example 23

Explanation: This command reads ASCII files where there is a single column. The command reads this one column from a single file as a Y value to the actual page. If the 'omit' parameter is present, the command will omit the first 'omit' lines of the file (if there is some text, explanation, etc. at the beginning of the file). X values will be serial numbers.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*") all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and the column numbers where the spectrum is read.

Command: **READ** 'filename'

Example: read example

Explanation: This command is reading the old (DOS version) SpServ files. If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*") all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last filename is read.

The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

Command: IRBR 'filename'

Example: IRBR example

Explanation: This command is reading the files produced by a Brooker IR spectrometer. Brooker has changed the file structure during the years, so not all Brooker file formats are recognized. For sure the files produced by Brooker IFS66 can be read by this command, other Brooker spectrometers were not checked. If in doubt please export the spectra as ASCII files and use the RAXY or RAY command.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*") all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

Command: **IRPU** 'filename'

Example: irpu example

Explanation: This command is reading the files produced by a Pye Unicam (Nicolet) IR spectrometer. Pye Unicam has changed the file structure during the years, so not all Pye Unicam file formats are recognized. For sure the files produced by Pye Unicam 9800 can be read by this command, other Pye Unicam spectrometers were not checked. If in doubt please export the spectra as ASCII files and use the RAXY or RAY command.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. "exam*") all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

Command: **IRP5** 'filename'

Example: IRP5 example

Explanation: This command reads the files produced by a Pye Unicam IR spectrometer but from a different file structure. Pye Unicam has changed the file structure during the years, so not all Pye Unicam file formats are recognized. For sure the files produced by Pye Unicam 9800 can be read by this command, other Pye Unicam spectrometers were not checked. If in doubt please export the spectra as ASCII files and use the RAXY or RAY command.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. exam*) all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

Command: IRPE 'filename'

Example: IRPE example

Explanation: This command is reading the files produced by a Perkin Elmer IR spectrometer. Perkin Elmer has changed the file structure over the years, so not all Perkin Elmer file formats are recognized. For sure the files produced by Perkin Elmer XXXXXX can be read by this command, other Perkin Elmer spectrometers were not checked. If in doubt please export the spectra as ASCII files and use the RAXY or RAY command.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. exam*) all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

Command: RBESR 'filename'

Example: RBESR example

Explanation: This command is reading the files produced by a Bruker EPR spectrometer. Bruker has changed the file structure over the years, and two file formats are recognized (*.spc *.par pairs, and *.dta *.dsc pairs). If in doubt please export the spectra as ASCII files and use the RAXY or RAY command.

If the filename is unique, the file will be read into the current page. If the filename is not unique (e.g. exam*) all the files will be read into consecutive pages. After the command, the current page will be the page where the last file is read. The title of the page will contain the filename and also other parameter information if they are available.

File output commands

Command: **FTBL** filename from to any

Example: FTbl example 2 5

Explanation: This command exports the content of the pages from the 'from' page up to the 'to' page into an ASCII file. If parameter 'any' is present (it can be any character) the ASCII file contains columns in (XY XY XY XY XY) structure. If parameter 'any' is missing the ASCII file contains only ne X column (the first one) and Y values are in consecutive columns (XYYYYYY ... Y) structure.

All but 'any' parameters are necessary, if any of them is missing an error message will be presented.

Command: **FAXY** filename

Example: FAXY example

Explanation: This command exports the (X,Y) pairs of the current page into an ASCII file. The file will contain two ASCII columns (X and Y values).

Command: **SAVE**

Example: save example

Explanation: This command will save the whole SpServ session as a single “*.sps” file. if a filename is given then it will save with that file name. If the filename is not given it will save with the current file name. If there is no current file name the command will ask for it.

Command: **FCOMP** filename resolution

Example: `fcomp example.ext 3000`

Explanation: This command will save the spectrum, the fit, and all the fitted components in an Excel or CSV file depending on the file extension. If the extension is 'XLS' it will create an Excel file. If the extension is 'CSV' or if there is no extension it will create a comma-separated file. If there is no extension, the extension of the created file will be 'TXT'.

The 'resolution' parameter determines how many points the fitted curves will have. If no 'resolution' is given, the fitted curves will be calculated only at the points of the spectrum.

Administrative commands

Command: **REST**

Example: rest

Explanation: This command will open a brand new session in the SpServ program (like at the beginning of the program). If the previous session is not saved the command will ask if we are willing to save it.

Command: **ACT** parm1

Example: ACT 412

Explanation: parm1 is the 'new page to display'

The command changes the actual page to the given page number (parm1). The background will be the same. If the page number did not exist before it will create all the missing pages up to the parm1.

Command: +

Example: +

Explanation: Increase the current page number by one. If the page number did not exist before the command will create it. You can achieve the same effect by hitting the “up arrow” or “Page up” buttons on the keyboard or by clicking on the ‘→’ symbol on the upright corner of the main window. This command is useful in procedures.

Command: -

Example: -

Explanation: Decrease the current page number by one. If the actual page number is 1 nothing happens. You can achieve the same effect by hitting the “down arrow” or “Page down” buttons on the keyboard or by clicking on the ‘←’ symbol on the upright corner of the main window. This command is useful in procedures.

Command: **BACK**

Example: BACK

Explanation: Put the current page in the background.

Command: COPY from to how_many

Example: COPY

COPY 2

COPY 3 67

Copy 1 44 7

Explanation: The command copies the 'from' page to the 'to' page. If the 'to' page does not exist it will create all the missing pages up to the parameter 'to'+ 'how_many'. If parameter 'to' is not present the page 'from' will be copied to the background. If both 'from' and 'to' parameters are missing the current page is copied to the background.

If the 'how_many' parameter is present then 'how_many' pages will be copied starting from parameter 'from' up to 'from'+ 'how_many' to the pages 'to'+ 'how_many'.

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Command: **MOVE** from to how_many

Example: MOVE

MOVE 2

MOVE 3 67

MOVE 1 44 7

Explanation: The command moves the 'from' page to the 'to' page. If the 'to' page does not exist it will create all the missing pages up to the parameter 'to'+ 'how_many'. If parameter 'to' is not present the page 'from' will be moved to the background. If both 'from' and 'to' parameters are missing the current page is moved to the background (same as BACK).

If the 'how_many' parameter is present then 'how_many' pages will be moved started from parameter 'from' up to 'from'+ 'how_many' to the pages 'to'+ 'how_many'.

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Command: **SHOW** par1 par2 par3 parn

Example: show 11 23 55

Explanation: This command will display all the pages listed after the command word (par1....parn). The current page is always displayed. This is useful if someone wants to compare different spectra on different pages. If parameters are missing then only the current page will be plotted.

One can normalize the different spectra to the size of the screen to make the comparison easier. To do this, mark the signal named 'MinMax' on the bottom-right side of the main window.

Command: **SON**

Example:

Explanation: This command switches the SpServ sounds on.
When starting the program and no SET command was issued before, this is the default.

Command: **SOFF**

Example:

Explanation: This command switches the SpServ sounds off. If you want the sound to be off by default, issue the SET command after switching the sound off.

Procedure-related commands

Command: **SET** (filename)

Example: set

Explanation: This command stores the procedures and several settings in your personal setting space. Next time when starting the program it will be loaded and all procedures and all settings will be available from the very beginning of the program usage.

If 'filename' is given, then the command will store all the procedures present in the sps file to the file "filename.spspr". You can load it back and add it to existing procedures with the LOADPR command.

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Command: **LOADPR** filename
LOADP filename

Example: loadpr example

Explanation: The command loads procedures from a file "filename.spsr" previously made by the SET command. All the procedures from the "filename.spsr" will be added to the procedures already present in the 'sps' file. The command does not check for duplicates. If duplicates are present always the first occurrence of the procedure will be executed. Also the 'DELPR procname' will delete only the first occurrence of the procedure.

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Command: `PROC 'procedure_name'`

Example: `proc exampleproc`

Explanation: SpServ procedure is a list of SpServ commands or procedures. They are executed sequentially.

The command opens the procedure editing window and you can write or edit the procedure. If the 'procedure name' exists then you can edit the procedure, if it is a new procedure (did not exist before) you can write a new procedure.

The procedure name should not be an existing SpServ command name because in this case the existing command would be executed instead of the procedure.

The first line of the procedure is the procedure name, all consecutive lines should be valid SpServ commands or other procedure names.

When you have finished writing/editing the procedure, you finish it by CTRL/ENTER.

Procedures can be saved by the SET command. It is convenient to save basic procedures with it.

Procedures are also saved with *.sps files, so measurement-specific procedures would be available when loading the *.sps file again.

Command: LISTPR
PROC

Example: listpr

Explanation: The command lists the existing procedures.

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Command: **DELPR** or **DELP** 'procedure name'

Example: `delp exampleproc`

Explanation: Removes the procedure, so it will not be executed anymore.

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Spectrum visualization commands

Command: **DELSP**

Example: `delsp 1 4 67-148`

Explanation: The command removes the pages listed. If an interval is given (e.g. 7-148) all the pages in the interval, including the first and the last pages, will be removed.

The sequential number of the pages will change, and no empty pages will be left after removal.

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Command: **CHTI**

Example: `chti`

Explanation: The title is a one-line description of the spectrum. With this command, you can edit the title. The command opens a new window and you can write/edit the title.

Command: **MIMA** par1 par2

Example: mima 0 100

Explanation: The command changes the Y limits of the display. If both par1 and par2 are missing, the Y limits will automatically be set to 'auto', and the whole spectrum range (from minimum to maximum of the spectra) will be visible.

If both par1 and par2 are given, then the Y limits of the display will be set to par1 and par2 values.

This is an obsolete command (from the DOS version). You still can use it, but the magnifying glass icon on the toolbar is a better option.

Command: **XMIMA** par1 par2

Example: xmima 0 100

Explanation: The command changes the X limits of the display. If both par1 and par2 are missing, the X limits will automatically be set to 'auto', and the whole spectrum range (from minimum to maximum of the spectra) will be visible.

If both par1 and par2 are given, then the X limits of the display will be set to par1 and par2 values.

This is an obsolete command (from the DOS version). You still can use it, but the magnifying glass icon on the toolbar is a better option.

Command: **LIMS** from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn ton
ROI from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn ton

Example: roi 1 45 56 78

Explanation: This command specifies the regions of interest of the spectrum (especially for fitting).

The parameters in pairs should define the starting and end points of the region as channel numbers. If parameter 'to' is missing, then the limit will be extended to the last point of the spectrum.

The same effect can be achieved by clicking on the "Select limits graphically" icon on the toolbar or issuing the **GLIMS** command.

Command: **LIMSADD** from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn
ton

ROIADD from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn
ton

Example: roiadd 1 45 56 78

Explanation: This command adds new regions of interest to the already specified regions of interest of the spectrum.

The parameters in pairs should define the starting and end points of the region as channel numbers.

The same effect can be achieved by clicking on the “Select limits graphically’ icon on the toolbar or issuing the **GLIMS** command.

Command: **XLIMS** from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn
ton

XROI from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn ton

Example: xroi 1 45 56 78

Explanation: This command specifies the regions of interest of the spectrum (especially for fitting).

The parameters in pairs should define the starting and end points of the region as X values pairwise. If parameter 'to' is missing, the ROI will be extended to the end of the spectrum.

The same effect can be achieved by clicking on the "Select limits graphically" icon on the toolbar or issuing the **GLIMS** command.

Command: **XLIMSADD** from1 to 1 from2
to2.....fromn ton

XROIADD from1 to 1 from2 to2.....fromn
ton

Example: xroiadd 1 45 56 78

Explanation: This command adds new regions of interest to the already specified regions of interest of the spectrum.

The parameters in pairs should define the starting and end points of the region as X values pairwise.

The same effect can be achieved by clicking on the “Select limits graphically’ icon on the toolbar or issuing the **GLIMS** command.

Command: **GLIMS** (GROI)

Example: glims

Explanation: The command sets the regions of interest graphically. A new window will appear where you can select if you want to add a new region or finish the selection, and a blue rectangle will appear above the spectrum. In the beginning, the whole spectral range is selected, you can move the range or change it by using the selection marks. If you select 'Add' on the separate window, you can draw a rectangle to select a new region of interest.

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Command: **ZOOM** 'ROI number'

Example: zoom 2

Explanation: The command will set the X limits of the display to the X limits of the defined 'ROI number'. ROI number is the serial number of ROIs defined either with **LIMS**, **XLIMS**, or **GLIMS** commands.

Command: **NOZM (NOZOOM)**

Example: nozoom

Explanation: The command restores the X limits of the display to 'auto', consequently the whole X range of the spectrum will be visible.

Spectrum manipulation commands

Command: **CHNU** par

Example: chnu 1024

Explanation: This command will change the number of spectral points (channel number) on the current page. It is useful if you want to cut the end of the spectrum, or if you want to fill later manually the points. If you increase the channel number the X values will be serial numbers from the current channel number+1. Since X values are always sorted this might cause confusion when filling the points.

Command: **CHCO**

Example: `chco`

Explanation: The command (Change Content) allows you to change the points in the spectrum. A new window will be shown, where two columns for X and Y values will be present. You can edit any value. If you want to add a new value you can do it by moving the cursor by the keyboard while it is on the first or at the last row. A new row would be open at the very end of the columns, which can be filled.

The editing can be finished by pushing the ESCAPE button on the keyboard or by clicking on the 'Done' button.

The spectrum will be sorted according to X values after finishing the edit.

Command: ADD par
 ADDC par
 FG+C par

Example: add 4

Explanation: This command will add 'par' to every Y value on the current page. Useful if you want to shift vertically the spectra.

Command: **MULT** par
FG*C par

Example: mult 4

Explanation: This command will multiply every Y value on the current page by 'par'.

Command: **DIVE** par
 FG/C par

Example: dive 4

Explanation: This command will divide every Y value on the current page by 'par'.

Command: **ADDX** par

Example: addx 345

Explanation: This command will add a 'par' value to every X value on the current page. This will shift the X-axis.

Command: **MULTX** par

Example: multx 44

Explanation: This command will multiply every X value on the current page by 'par'.

Command: **DIVEX** par

Example: divex 45.55

Explanation: This command will divide every X value on the current page by 'par'.

Command: **FG-A** from to

Example: fg-a 23 45

Explanation: This command first calculates the average of the channel values from parameter 'from' to parameter 'to' and then this average is subtracted from the Y values on the current page. If any parameter is missing nothing happens.

Parameters 'from' and 'to' are channel numbers, not X values.

Command: **FG/A** from to

Example: FG/a 34 666

Explanation: This command first calculates the average of the channel values from parameter 'from' to parameter 'to' and then Y values in the current page are divided by this average. If any parameter is missing nothing happens.

Parameters 'from' and 'to' are channel numbers, not X values.

Command: FG+B

Example: fg+b

Explanation: This command adds the Y values from the current page to the Y values from the background. The results will be on the current page. The number of spectral points should be the same on the current page (foreground) and in the background. If the X values are different on the two pages, the X values from the current page (foreground) are used.

Command: FG-B

Example: fg-b

Explanation: This command subtracts the Y values of the background from the Y values of the current page. The results will be on the current page. The number of spectral points should be the same on the current page (foreground) and in the background. If the X values are different on the two pages, the X values from the current page (foreground) are used.

Command: **FG*B**

Example: fg*b

Explanation: This command multiplies the Y values of the background with the Y values of the current page. The results will be on the current page. The number of spectral points should be the same on the current page (foreground) and in the background. If the X values are different on the two pages, the X values from the current page (foreground) are used.

Command: FG/B

Example: fg/b

Explanation: This command divides the Y values of the current page with the Y values of the background. The results will be on the current page. The number of spectral points should be the same on the current page (foreground) and in the background. If the X values are different on the two pages, the X values from the current page (foreground) are used.

Command: **FGUB**

Example: fgub

Explanation: This command unionizes the foreground (current page) and the background. The number of spectral points will be the sum of the foreground and the background. X values are sorted after the union.

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Command: **FGNORM**

Example: fgnorm

Explanation: This command normalizes the foreground spectrum and puts the result in the background. It calculates the normalized spectrum as:

$$y_{\text{norm}} = (y - y_{\text{min}}) / (y_{\text{max}} - y_{\text{min}})$$

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Command: **FG-BL**

Example: fg-bl

Explanation: This command subtracts the baseline values of the fit from the Y values of the current page. The results will be on the background page.

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Command: **FG-FIT**

Example: fg-fit

Explanation: This command subtracts the fitted curve values from the Y values of the current page. The results will be on the background page.

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Command: **SMOOTH** par1 par2 par3 par4

Example: smooth sg 10 10 21

Explanation: This command.....

Smooth the spectrum in the foreground. The result will be in the background. There are different types of smoothing, depending on the first parameter.

- par1=13, par2=repeat: Fits a linear curve to 3 points (-1 0 +1, regarding the point to smooth), and repeats 'repeat' times. Example: "smooth 13 100", performs the type 13 smoothing 100 times.
- par1=15, par2=repeat: Fits a linear curve to 5 points (-2 -1 0 +1 +2, regarding the point to smooth), and repeats 'repeat' times. Example: "smooth 15 100", performs the type 15 smoothing 100 times.
- par1=35, par2=repeat: Fits a cubic curve to 5 points (-2 -1 0 +1 +2, regarding the point to smooth), and repeats 'repeat' times. Example: "smooth 35 100", performs the type 35 smoothing 100 times.
- par1=MA par2=window(default=9 points): Calculates the moving average using 'window' wide window. Example "smooth MA 13" calculates moving average with 11 point window. The window is always centered to the point to smooth.
- par1=SG par2=span (default=21) par3=degree (default=10): Calculates the Soletzky-Golay smoothing with the parameters given. Example: smooth SG 33 12 calculates Soletzky-Golay smoothing with span=33 and degree=12.

Command: PINT par mode

Example: pint 7 sum

Explanation: The command reduces the number of spectral points by adding the spectral points in the window determined by 'par'. For example, PINT 2 will add (and divide by 2) two neighboring points, and the resulting spectrum will have $n/2$ data points. If 'par' is omitted the mean of every second point will be calculated.

The mode parameter determines if the mean or the sum will be calculated. If mode='sum', then the command simply adds the points together. If the mode is anything else or if it is omitted the command will calculate the mean of the data points in the group.

The result will always be in the background.

Command: **DIFF** par from to

Example: diff 7

Explanation: The command calculates the differential of the spectrum, depending on the value of par, in the region [from to]. If from and to parameters are missing, the differential of the whole spectrum will be calculated.

If par=5, par=7, or par=9, it calculates the differential using a 5, 7, or 9-channel window. These 'par' values can be used ONLY if the spectrum X values are equidistant.

For any other 'par' value the command calculates the neighbor difference:

$$Y_{i_new} = \frac{Y_{i+1} - Y_i}{X_{i+1} - X_i}$$

values. It can be used even if the X values are NOT equidistant.

Command: **DDIFF**

Example:

Explanation: The command calculates the double differential (differential of the differential) of the whole spectrum, depending on the value of par.

If par=7, or par=9, it calculates the differential using a 7, or 9-channel window. The command can be used **ONLY** if the spectrum X values are equidistant.

Command: SVD 'start spectrum' 'stop spectrum'
'number of SVD components'

Example: SVD number

SVD start stop

SVD start stop SVDnum

Explanation: Calculates the SVD matrices of the spectra.

- SVD 'number': calculates the SVD of the first 'number' spectra (from 1 to 'number'). "SVD 13" will calculate the SVD of the first 13 spectra.
- SVD 'start' 'stop' ('start' < 'stop'): calculates the SVD of the spectra from 'start' up to 'stop' spectra. "SVD 12 24" will calculate the SVD of the spectra from spectrum 12 up to spectrum 24.
- SVD 'number' 'SVDnum' ('number' > 'SVDnum'): calculates the SVD of the first 'number' spectra, and returns only the first 'SVDnum' SVD components. "SVD 33 5" will calculate the SVD of the first 33 spectra (pages 1-33) and returns 5 SVD components.
- SVD 'start' 'stop' 'SVDnum': calculates the SVD of the spectra from 'start' up to 'stop' spectra, and returns only the first 'SVDnum' components. "SVD 12 24 5" will calculate the SVD of the spectra from spectrum 12 up to spectrum 24 and return 5 SVD components.

The results will be located after the current maximum number of spectra. First, the 'SVDnum' number of column vectors of the S matrix, then the weight of the components (W) followed by the 'SVDnum' number of row vectors of the V matrix.

Command: **ISVD** 'start of S spectra' 'start of V spectra' 'number of components'

Example: ISVD 101 121 5

Explanation: This command calculates the inverse SVD of the components. The first parameter is the serial number of the page where S spectra begin, the second parameter is the serial number of the page where V spectra begin, and the third parameter is the number of components we want to include in the inverse SVD calculation. The W numbers should be on the page just before the V spectra.

If you do not want to include a specific component (e. g. the 5th component) but include the subsequent components, the corresponding W value (e. g. W(5)) should be set to zero (using the **CHCO** command).

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **BLCORR**

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: **INTG** 'from channel' 'to channel'

Example:

Explanation:

Command: **MIRROR**

Example:

Explanation:

Command: **INTX**

Example:

Explanation:

Command: **SQRX**

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: **SQRY**

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: LOGX

Example:

Explanation:

Command: **LOGY**

Example:

Explanation:

Command: **DELE** 'from' 'to' 'constant'

Example: dele 1 100 4

Explanation:

The command will change the spectrum values from 'from' channel to 'to' channel. The new spectrum value will be the 'constant' value. If the 'constant' parameter is missing the value is zero. If the 'constant' parameter is not a number, the channels will be removed from the spectrum.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: ACF

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: IP

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: XSH

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: CHSP

Example:

Explanation:

Command: SHIFT

Example:

Explanation:

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Command: **AVGE**

Example:

Explanation:

Command: FFT 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'
FFTC 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'

Example: FFT 1 21 100000

Explanation: Calculates the FFT of the spectrum. The 'from' parameter is the page number of the source spectrum, which will be Fourier transformed, the result will be located on the 'to' page. The 'extend' parameter means the extension of the spectrum to the nearest upper second power.

The resulting spectrum will have complex numbers.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **FFTX** 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'
FFTABS 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'

Example: **FFTX** 1 21 100000

Explanation: Calculates the FFT of the spectrum. The 'from' parameter is the page number of the source spectrum, which will be Fourier transformed, the result will be located on the 'to' page. The 'extend' parameter means the extension of the spectrum to the nearest upper second power.

The resulting spectrum will contain the absolute value of the FFT transform.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **FFTPOW** 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'
FFTPOWER 'from' 'to' 'extend' 'how many'

Example: **FFTPOW** 1 21 100000

Explanation: Calculates the FFT of the spectrum. The 'from' parameter is the page number of the source spectrum, which will be Fourier transformed, the result will be located on the 'to' page. The 'extend' parameter means the extension of the spectrum to the nearest upper second power.

The resulting spectrum will contain the power spectrum (square of the absolute value of the FFT transform).

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Command: **FFTS** 'from' 'to' 'extend'

Example:

Explanation: Calculates the inverse FFT of the spectrum. The

Command: IFFT 'from' 'to' 'extend'

Example:

Explanation: Calculates the inverse FFT of the spectrum. The 'from' parameter is the page number of the source spectrum, which will be inverse Fourier transformed, the result will be located in the 'to' page. The 'extend' parameter means the extension of the spectrum to the nearest upper second power.

The resulting spectrum will have complex numbers.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **CABS** 'from' 'to' 'how many'

Example:

Explanation: Calculates the absolute value of the spectrum on page 'from' (spectrum should be complex) and puts it to the page 'to'. If the parameter 'how many' is also given it repeats the procedure that many times on consecutive pages. If no parameter is given then the calculation will be performed on the current page and the result will be in the background.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **CREAL** 'from' 'to' 'how many'

Example:

Explanation: Calculates the real part of the spectrum on page 'from' (spectrum should be complex) and puts it to the page 'to'. If the parameter 'how many' is also given it repeats the procedure that many times on consecutive pages. If no parameter is given then the calculation will be performed on the current page and the result will be in the background.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **CIMAG** 'from' 'to' 'how many'

Example:

Explanation: Calculates the imaginary part of the spectrum on page 'from' (spectrum should be complex) and puts it to the page 'to'. If the parameter 'how many' is also given it repeats the procedure that many times on consecutive pages. If no parameter is given then the calculation will be performed on the current page and the result will be in the background.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Fitting functions

Command: LORENTZ

Example: lorentz

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the Lorentz function. Lorentz function has 3 parameters, amplitude (or intensity), peak position, and peak width (FWHM). The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = \frac{A}{1 + \left(\frac{X - X_0}{\Gamma}\right)^2}$$

where A is the amplitude, X_0 is the peak position, and Γ is the peak width (FWHM).

Command: GAUSS

Example: gauss

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the Gauss function. Gauss function has 3 parameters, amplitude (or intensity), peak position, and peak width (FWHM). The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X - X_0}{\Gamma/\ln(2)}\right)^2\right)$$

where A is the amplitude, X_0 is the peak position, and Γ is the peak width (FWHM).

Command: **EXP**

Example: exp

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the exponential function. The exponential function has 2 parameters, amplitude, and decay time. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \exp\left(-\frac{X}{\tau}\right)$$

where A is the amplitude and τ is the decay time

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: SAT

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the saturation function. The saturation function has 2 parameters, amplitude, and decay time. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{X}{\tau}\right) \right)$$

where A is the amplitude and τ is the decay time

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: LOG

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the logarithmic function. The logarithmic function has 2 parameters, amplitude, and position (singularity point). The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \log(X - X_0)$$

where A is the amplitude and X_0 is the singularity point.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: EXPJ

Example: expj

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the exponential jump function. It is also known as the Fermi function or logistic function. The exponential jump function has 3 parameters, amplitude, transition position, and transition width. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = \frac{A}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{X - X_0}{\Gamma}\right)}$$

where A is the amplitude X_0 is the transition position, and Γ is the transition width.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **EXPJU**

Example:

Explanation:

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: ATAN

Example: atan

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the arcus tangent function. The arcus tangent function has 3 parameters, amplitude, transition position, and transition width. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = \frac{A}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2}{\pi} \operatorname{atan} \left(\frac{X - X_0}{\Gamma} \right) \right)$$

where A is the amplitude X_0 is the transition position, and Γ is the transition width.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: POWER

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the power function. The power function has 3 parameters, amplitude, shift, and power. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A(X - X_0)^n$$

where A is the amplitude, X_0 is the shift, and n is the power. 'n' should be positive and can be less than 1.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: SPM

Example: spm

Explanation: Spectrum mix command. This is useful if the spectrum can be constructed as a sum of different other spectra. This function has 3 parameters, amplitude (this is the contribution of the spectrum), position (this is the page number where the spectrum is located, and it is always kept constant), and shift (it is usually 0, and you should fix it, but if the X values are slightly shifting you can unlock this parameter).

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: SIN

Example: sin

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the sinus function. The sinus function has 3 parameters, amplitude, time of period, and phase. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \sin\left(2\pi\left(\frac{X + \Phi}{T}\right)\right)$$

where A is the amplitude, Φ is the phase, and T is the time of period.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: SINEX

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to an exponentially decaying sinus function. The exponentially decaying sinus function has 4 parameters, amplitude, time of period, phase, and decay time. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A * \exp\left(-\frac{X}{\tau}\right) * \sin\left(2\pi\left(\frac{X - \Phi}{T}\right)\right)$$

where A is the amplitude, Φ is the phase, T is the time of period, and τ is the decay time.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: EXPLIN

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the exponential function multiplied by the independent variable. This is very useful if you have two exponential functions with slightly different t values and with different signs. In this case, two exponentials will not give a good fit.

This function has 3 parameters, amplitude, shift, and decay time. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A * (X - X_0) * \exp\left(-\frac{X}{\tau}\right)$$

where A is the amplitude and τ is the decay time.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: EXPSEC

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the exponential function multiplied by the square of the independent variable. This function has 3 parameters, amplitude, shift, and decay time. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A * (X - X_0)^2 * \exp\left(-\frac{X}{\tau}\right)$$

where A is the amplitude and τ is the decay time.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: **ARRH**

Example:

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the Arrhenius function. The Arrhenius function has 2 parameters, amplitude, and activation energy. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R * X}\right)$$

where A is the amplitude, E_a is the activation energy. The R is the molar gas constant (8.31446261815324 J/K/mol)

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: MICHMEN

Example: michmen

Explanation: This command will set the fitting function to the Michaelis-Menten kinetics. This function has 2 parameters, the maximum velocity, and the so-called Michaelis-Menten constant. The form of the function is the following:

$$Y = \frac{V_{max} * X}{X + K_m}$$

where V_{max} is the maximal velocity, and K_m is the Michaelis-Menten constant.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: MIXED

Example:

Explanation: By using this command you can mix all the functions. For example, it can be fitted the spectrum with a Lorentz function on an exponential background. Or fit a Lorentian and a Gaussian peak on the same spectrum.

The "Parameter window" will change after issuing this command. The column where there are the names of the functions will change to a pull-down window and you can select what function you want to include in the fit.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Administration of fitting commands

Command: **AMPL**

Example: `ampl`

Explanation: In the case of peak functions it calculates the amplitude (peak height) value instead of intensity (area below the peak). Can be used **ONLY** for peak functions. This is the default.

Command: **INTS**

Example: ints

Explanation: In the case of peak functions it calculates the intensity (area below the peak) value instead of amplitude (peak height). Can be used ONLY for peak functions.

Command: **FREQ**

Example: freq

Explanation: X values are treated as frequency scale (i.e. as they are), not wavelength scale. It can **ONLY** be used for peak functions. This is the default.

Command: **WAVE**

Example:

Explanation: X values are treated as wavelength scales, not as they are. In fitting the reciprocal value of X values will be used. It can ONLY be used for peak functions.

Command: FF 'channel number'

Example: ff 500

Explanation: This command will calculate the fit function in the background.

If the parameter 'channel number' is missing, the channel number of the background spectrum would be the same as it is in the ROIs of the foreground and the same X values would be used as they are in the ROIs of the foreground (the spectra will match).

If the parameter 'channel number' is 'f' then the channel number would be the same as in the foreground and the same X values would be used as they are in the foreground (the spectra will match).

If the parameter 'channel number' is a number then the background will have this channel number and the X values will be evenly distributed along the displayed region.

Command: **COMP**

Example: `comp`

Explanation: The command will display the different components (unique functions, and the baseline) separately on the display with a blue color.

Command: **STFIT**

Example: stfit

Explanation: This will store the fitting parameters of the spectrum. You can recall it using the **RFIT** command.

Command: **RFIT** 'fit number'

Example: rfit 'fit number'

Explanation: The command recalls one of the previously stored fits.

If 'fit number' is a positive integer then that fit will be restored.

If the 'fit number' is 0, then the last stored fit will be restored.

If the 'fit number' is a negative number then that fit before the last fit will be restored.

If the 'fit number' is missing a list of stored fits will appear and you can select which fit should be restored. All stored fits have a short description to help select the fit.

Command: **CLEANFIT** remain

Example: cleanfit 11

Explanation: It will delete the previously stored fits and only the last 'remain' number of fits will be available.

'remain' should be larger than 5, if it is smaller, the last 5 fits would be available.

Fitting commands

Command: **PARM** 'number of peaks' 'baseline power'

Example:

Explanation: The command sets the number of functions, and the baseline to be fit.

The parameter 'number of peaks' determines how many different functions should be added (e.g. how many peaks are in a spectrum). The parameter 'baseline power' would determine the power of the polynomial used as the baseline.

If the 'baseline power' parameter is missing a constant baseline (0th power) will be used. If the 'baseline power' parameter is -1, then no baseline will be fit.

issuing this command the Parameter window will change according to the number of functions and baseline power, and you can fill in the different initial fitting parameters. The previously set parameter values will be unchanged.

Command: SORTPARAM parm

Example: sortparm 3

Explanation: This command will sort the functions in the 'Parameter window' according to their parameters. The 'parm' parameter will determine according to which parameter you want to sort the functions. The default is 2, so the sorting will use the second parameter of the function (e.g. in the case of Lorentz functions it is the 'position' parameter). The sorting is in increasing order. If you want to sort in decreasing order use negative 'parm' values.

If the function to fit is Lorentzian, then the command

sortparm 3

will sort the functions by their width values in increasing order, while the command

sortparm -1

will sort the functions by their amplitude values in decreasing order.

ONLY FOR PROFESSIONAL VERSION

Command: FIT

Example: fit

Explanation: The command will perform a fit on the current (actual) spectrum by the function selected and with the parameter set given in the 'Parameter window'.

The fit will stop if

- i./A good fit has been achieved.
- ii./The maximum iteration limit has been reached. You can repeat the fit until it terminates successfully, or change the limit of iteration to 'not checked' in the 'Parameter window'.
- iii./ The iteration steps are too little. It might mean that your initial parameters are way off, so you might consider changing them. You also might consider changing either the 'Cage on' or 'Stop if too little steps' radio buttons to the 'unset' value on the 'Parameter window'.

Unset the 'Stop if too little steps' radio button will prevent stopping and might let the fit converge. Unset 'Cage on' might completely destabilize the parameters. Use both cases with care.

- iv./ The matrix inversion has failed. It means that something is going wrong with your fit and the parameter matrix is probably wrong. Set new initial parameters, or fix some parameters.

Command: **RESCSV** filename

Example: rescsv filename

Explanation: This command produces a CSV (Comma-Separated Values file) (*.csv) and outputs the fitting results.

If the parameter 'filename' is given, then it will produce a filename.csv file. If the parameter is missing the filename will be 'SpServ_results_date.csv, for example,

SpServ_results_04-Aug-2022.csv.

If the file exists the results will be appended, if the file does not exist it will be created. The names of individual fitting parameters are in the first, header row of the file.

Command: **RESXLS** filename

Example: resxls filename

Explanation: This command produces an Excel file (*.xls) and outputs the fitting results.

If the parameter 'filename' is given, then it will produce a filename.xls file. If the parameter is missing the filename will be 'SpServ_results_date.xls', for example,

SpServ_results_04-Aug-2022.xls.

If the file exists the results will be appended, if the file does not exist it will be created. The names of individual fitting parameters are in the first, header row of the file.

Command: **RSLT**

Example:

Explanation:

This command is obsolete.